

PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIP DURING THE NEW NORMAL EDUCATION LANDSCAPE

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Parent-Child Relationship During the New Normal Education Landscape

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the influence of parent-child relationship to pupils' childhood development skills. Results show that parents extraordinarily develop a "high extent" child relationship; pupils' childhood development of skills was found to be "slightly advanced developed" and it was found out that parent-child relationship promotes pupils' childhood development skills. It was recommended that the school head and teachers should stimulate and encourage collaboration with parents in order to create and provide more parent-child interactive learning which emphasized the development of life-long skills. Lastly, an empirical research on the factors that influence parent-child cohesiveness should likewise be conducted to explore further the enormous contribution of parent-child relationship to pupils' childhood development skills.

Keywords: *parent-child relationship, childhood development skills, highly advanced development, slightly advanced development*

Introduction

The relationship between a parent and kid fosters the youngster's social, emotional, and physical growth. Every child and parent may cherish and grow this special link. The basis for the child's personality, decisions in life, and general behavior is laid by this interaction. It can also affect the strength of their social, physical, mental and emotional health.

The framework of the study is anchored on Article 77 of Chapter 2 of the Presidential Decree No. 603 also known as "Child and Youth Welfare Code" of the Education Act of 1982 which defines the role of parents in basic education to provide support and collaborate in the education of children through full cooperation of parents in effective and efficient implementation of curriculum and school programs.

Alampay (2019) suggests that the connections between a parent and their child are a key predictor of the child's early emotional and social progress. These interactions are a traditional research object in development psychology.

It was emphasized that children thrive in a positive environment, so hearing compliments, stating clear expectations for positive behaviors, and positively engaging with the child should enhance self-confidence and the development of communication and healthy habits.

Furthermore, Dela Cruz (2015) found that research on parent-child relationships constantly shows a positive correlation between parental involvement in children's education and their academic performance. Additionally, positive parent-child relationships are linked to helpful outcomes for children, such as reduced truancy and lower dropout rates.

Consequently, Melgar (2015) argued that a strong parent-child relationship enhances parental commitment in their children's education, resulting in positive impacts on students. He also studied the factors that affect parental engagement in their children's schooling and explored the roles that schools and teachers can play in promoting this involvement.

Pangilinan (2019) noted that the main element influencing children's academic habits is their relationship with their parents. Parent-child relationships are intricate constructs that have been shown to improve academic performance. Furthermore, studies specify that the most significant influence of these relationships on children's academic success stems from parents' encouragement and expressed aspirations for their children to pursue higher education.

Javier (2019) found that the parent-child bond boosts students' academic performance by fostering their enthusiasm and engagement in the classroom. Although numerous studies have identified a correlation between family members' involvement and children's academic success, these studies often concentrate on demographic factors like socioeconomic status. Additionally, it was also emphasized that parents' level of relationship with children affect the parents' level of engagement in school activities. Parents with higher relationship with children tend to participate more in school activities and provide support for their children to succeed in school.

As a result, Marzano (2014) found that strong parent-child relationships and students' behavioral and emotional involvement improved performance; however, they failed to mention the connections between student engagement in school and parent-teacher relationships. Not every research, although, has indicated a good correlation between students' involvement in school and parent-child relationships.

Further, it was emphasized that in order to help pupils improve their school performance, teachers need to collaborate with parents to develop partnership with their children. Teachers need to emphasize the role of home relationship especially in the new normal educational landscape.

Home environment which is predictive of the parent-child positive relationship is one of the primary variables that predict pupils'

school performance. Moreover, there is a widely held belief that parents who cultivate a supportive learning environment at home significantly influence the development of their children's academic benefits, thereby enhancing their academic achievement.

However, the researcher was inspired to conduct this study in order to provide a deeper understanding and explore the ways in which parental relationship with children influences academic performance of the secondary school students in Villanueva National High School of Villanueva North District, Division of Misamis Oriental, because there is a dearth of readily available and accessible information on the relationship between parents and children and students' academic successes in public schools.

Research Questions

The study sought to assess how the parent-child relationship influences the learning outcomes of kindergarten students at West City Central School, Division of Cagayan de Oro City, for the academic year 2023-2024. The study aimed to address the following questions:

1. How is the parent-child relationship defined in this study?
2. What is the early childhood development skills of pupils as indicated in the result of Early Childhood Developmental Checklist categorized as:
 - 2.1. highly advanced development;
 - 2.2. slightly advance development;
 - 2.3. average overall development;
 - 2.4. slight delay in overall development; and
 - 2.5. significant delay in overall development?
3. Does a meaningful correlation exist between early childhood development skills and the parent-child relationship?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the correlational- descriptive research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2012) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adapted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The study's participants include parents and kindergarten students from West City Central School throughout the academic year 2023-2024.

One hundred (100) parents and pupils participated in the survey questionnaire regarding the parent-child relationship and early childhood development skills, respectively. The responses were casually selected for the convenience of the researcher.

Instrument

The survey used in this study to assess how parent-child relationships impact students' learning outcomes was modified from Lara et al. (2019).

The survey instrument contains of two main parts. Early childhood development skills are characterised into two sections: the parent-child relationship, which is measured using ten (10) indicators, and the overall development of the child, which is measured using five categories: highly advanced, slightly advanced, average, slightly delayed, and significantly delayed.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and School Principal to conduct the study.

Subsequently, the researcher asked a parental consent from the parents to use their children as the respondents and ask help from them to assist their children in answering the survey questionnaire. They were given an assurance for the confidentiality of the data.

After the respondents answered the questionnaire, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment are utilized in the study:

Problem 1. The parent-child connection was shown using the mean value and standard deviation.

Problem 2. The early childhood development abilities were presented using a range of scores and percentages.

Problem 3. The parent-child connection and early childhood development abilities were shown to be significantly correlated with Spearman-Rank Order Correlation, or Spearman-Rho.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on parent-child relationship during the new normal education landscape. The data is analyzed and interpreted using the findings of a survey questionnaire designed to address the issues raised.

Problem 1: How does the parent-child relationship characterized in this study?

Table 1. Mean Distribution on Parent-Child Relationship

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Communicates aspirations to His/her child to excel in academic Activities in school.	3.88	.938	High Extent
2.) Nurtures physical, emotional and Social developments of the child.	3.78	.995	High Extent
3.) Develops trust and respect towards Towards his/her child.	3.80	1.010	High Extent
4.) Maintains open communication to His/her child.	3.84	.955	High Extent
5.) Helps child exhibits positive behavior.	3.82	.962	High Extent
6.) Creates a home environment of love And compassion.	3.70	1.054	High Extent
7.) Listens and empathizes with each Other.	3.58	1.089	High Extent
8.) Sets and discusses limits and roles.	3.58	1.089	High Extent
9.) Encourages his/her child to express Feelings.	3.60	1.069	High Extent
10.) Play games with family members.	3.60	1.069	High Extent
Overall Mean	3.72	1.023	High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Extremely High/3.41-4.20 High/2.62-3.40 Moderate/1.81-2.60 Low/1.00-1.80 Extremely low

Table 1 shows the mean distribution for the parent-child relationship. Overall, respondents assessed the parent-child connection as "High Extent" (mean = 3.7, SD = 1.023). This shows that parents have formed strong bonds with their children. The findings also indicate that parents communicate their expectations for their children to excel academically and in school activities, foster trust and respect, create a supportive home environment for the child's emotional, psychological, and social development, and maintain open communication.

The indicator which states that "communicates aspirations to his/her child to excel in academic activities in school" obtained the highest mean of 3.88 (SD=.938) which is verbally described as "High Extent". The result indicates that parents can communicate transparently to their children and can express their expectations especially in their academic achievements in school, what their parents want them to achieve and accomplish as well as identifying the roles their children will take in order to succeed academically. It can be deduced based on findings that parents had established that unique bond with their children where they take on the responsibility to inspire and constantly guide and communicate to their children their aspirations to succeed in their studies.

Adler and Puja (2023) asserted that parents who cultivate effective and close communication with their children can assist them in exploring interests beyond academics. They also underlined how parent-child connections affect a child's self-esteem, mental health, and other important components of well-being. It was also stressed how much simpler it is for parents to communicate their goals for their children when there is a healthy parent-child bond.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.58 (SD1.089) is verbally described as "High Extent" in the indicators "listens and empathizes with each other" and "sets and discusses limits and roles". The findings suggest that parents and kids listen to one another, show empathy, talk, and establish boundaries in accordance with their different responsibilities as parents and kids. These indicate that parents established positive relationship with their children and an environment of shared responsibilities is recognized which create a healthier home environment.

Casey (2022) emphasized that parents who foster solid connections with their children, characterized by active listening, empathy, and

clear limits about obligations and liberties, can effectively motivate children to excel in school and academic pursuits.

Problem 2: What is the early childhood development skills of pupils as indicated in the results of early childhood development skills checklist categorized as: Highly Advanced Development, Slightly Advanced Development, Average Overall Development, Slight Delay in Overall Development, Significant Delay in Overall Development?

Table 2. *Frequency Distribution in the Early Childhood Development Skills*

Development Skills	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Highly Advanced Development	11	22.0
Slightly Advanced Development	18	36.0
Average Overall Development	12	34.0
Slightly Delay in Overall Dev.	9	18.0
Significant Delay in Overall Dev.	0	0
Total	50	100.0

Table 2 displays the distribution of early childhood development skill levels. It reveals that 18 out of 50 pupils, or 36%, attained a "slightly advanced development" rating. Additionally, 12 pupils, or 34%, achieved an "average overall development" rating, whereas only 18% exhibited "slightly delayed overall development." No pupils were classified as significantly delayed in their overall development of early childhood skills. These results suggest that students demonstrated strong performance in early childhood development skills at school. The findings imply that the parent-child relationship has played a significant role in fostering these skills.

Marzano and Caro (2023) confirmed that the development of students' skills is impacted by parent-child relationships and parental support and engagement in learning. Parents' roles and their active involvement in the education of their children is crucial as it inspires and motivates children to develop good learning habits, participation in school and classroom activities, and foster an overall positive attitude towards education which is manifested by their children's learning achievements.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the early childhood development skills and the parent-child relationship?

Table 3. *Significant Relationship between Early Childhood Development skills and Parent-Child Relationship*

Relationship	Early Childhood Development Skills			
	(r_s)	P-Value 2-tailed	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1
Parent-Child Relationship	.934	.000	Shows very High Correlation	Rejected

*significant at $p < 0.05$ alpha level

Table 3 shows the results of the test for a significant correlation between the parent-child relationship and the level of early childhood development abilities. Results revealed that parent-child relationship shows very high correlation with early childhood development skills as evident by the r_s value of .934 which is greater than the p-value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

This result indicates that parent-child relationship greatly influenced development of childhood skills. Based on the findings, it can be inferred that students' skill development is linked to the parent-child relationship. This suggests that parents who nurture strong familial bonds with their children can effectively encourage and motivate them to learn, develop, and enhance their skills, which proves beneficial in their higher-level school and academic activities.

This finding was supported by Adler and Puja (2023) who emphasized that strong and higher parent-child relationship will inspire children develop social, personal, and life-long learning skills. It was also emphasized that a child who has secured relationship with parent learns to regulate emotions under stress and in difficult situations, promotes cognitive, social development, and emotional skills. It also promotes the child's excellent social habits. When parents engage positively in their children's daily lives, it ensures improved social and academic outcomes for their children.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it was resolved that overall, the parent-child relationship fosters the early childhood development of skills in pupils.

The study also indicated that the parents have created a high-level bond with their children; communicate their expectations to excel

in their academic and school activities; develop trust and respect, create a home environment supportive to their child's emotional, psychological, and social developments.

Subsequently, it can be clinched further that parent-child relationship influenced the childhoods development skills. This suggests that parents' capacity to build relationships with their children predicts the development of lifelong skills in the child.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations were being offered to be considered:

School heads are stimulated to continuously encourage teachers to collaborate parents in the development of childhoods' social and other life-long skills through the provision of contextualized learning materials which promote parents' involvement in the process.

Teachers are encouraged to develop rapport and collaboration with parents and help enhance parent-child relationship through school and class activities that involve and engage parents and help create a learning experience with the parents and child are greatly involved.

An empirical research on the factors that influence parent-child cohesiveness that promotes the development of child's life-long skills should likewise be conducted to explore variables that enormously stimulate development of pupils' childhood skills.

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